

PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN SOCIETY

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Abstract: The article describes social problems in the life of society. The types of existing social problems are listed. Ways to eliminate social problems are indicated.

Key words: community, social problems, neighborhood, low-income family, social support and services.

Society is a product of the union of people. They can consist of different nationalities and ethnic groups. Because their genesis, personal psychological characteristics, intellectual potential, worldview, upbringing, and beliefs are different, their lifestyle also varies. Therefore, the emergence of social problems is a natural phenomenon. But for a happy life, there are factors that determine the life of society. Russian sociologists classify this system of factors as follows:

- 1) material and spiritual culture;
- 2) a system of various symbols embodied in language and the spiritual experience of humanity;
- 3) a certain system of education and upbringing;
- 4) types of social life activity - labor, political and cognitive activity, as well as moral and religious relations;
- 5) interaction of representatives of different generations;
- 6) family and interethnic relations .

Every state, regardless of its state structure, ensures decent living conditions for its citizens. For our country, where representatives of 130 different nationalities and ethnic groups live, this issue is of urgent importance. After gaining national independence in 1991, Uzbekistan began to build a democratic state and civil society. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, developed the scientific and theoretical foundations for building a legal democratic state and civil society. From the first days of independence, great attention was paid to solving social problems through the mahalla system. In 1992, rural, aul, and mahalla citizens' assemblies were enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan as bodies of citizen self-government. Legal and regulatory documents have been implemented to ensure their activities and define their powers in social protection of citizens . As a result, the processes of socialization manifested themselves in citizens, and their features of participation in state affairs developed. More than 9,000 villages, auls, and citizens' assemblies have become a bridge between the state and the mahalla in ensuring the socio-spiritual atmosphere on the ground. Providing social assistance to low-income families, protecting motherhood and childhood, and addressing local issues have become practical examples of the "From a Strong State to a Strong Civil Society" principle. The following tasks:

- loyalty to national and universal values;
- preservation of centuries-old traditions and customs;

- the harmonious upbringing of the younger generation;
- establishment of public control;
- ensuring entrepreneurship and supporting the abilities of the population;
- improvement of the living conditions of citizens;
- provision of social assistance to families without a breadwinner and with disabilities;
- maximizing income from household plots and reducing poverty;
- engaging in handicrafts and ensuring employment of the population;
- improvement of mahalla infrastructure to create decent living conditions for the population;
- transformation of regions into a driver of product supply;
- systematic work is being carried out to develop citizens' participation in public administration.

The creation in 1992 at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the Republican Charitable Public Fund "Mahalla" played an important role in strengthening the material and technical base of citizens' gatherings, promoting national values in mahallas, strengthening cultural and educational work, and supporting socially vulnerable segments of the population.

After the transfer of the powers of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the end of 2016, the activities of citizens' self-government bodies reached a high level. In particular, at present, 9,532 citizens' assemblies in the republic are fully equipped with modern computer sets, and 7,746 with furniture. Over the past three years, about 40 manuals and literature have been prepared and delivered to citizens' assemblies. This contributes to the effectiveness of their activities.

The territorial structures of the Republican Charitable Public Fund "Mahalla" provided methodological and practical assistance in organizing more than 50 thousand educational and cultural events annually in mahallas. The annual traditional competitions "The Most Exemplary Citizens' Self-Government Bodies" and "The Most Exemplary Consultant of Citizens' Assemblies on Religious Enlightenment and Spiritual-Moral Education" also served to study the activities of citizens' assemblies in ensuring the implementation of relevant legislation and widely disseminate their best practices.

Currently, about 10,000 mahalla citizens' assemblies have become collective bodies for solving social problems. The creation in mahallas of public commissions on reconciliation, enlightenment and spirituality, social support, work with women, issues of minors, youth and sports, development of entrepreneurial activity and family business, ecology, nature protection, improvement and landscaping, public control and protection of consumer rights creates new opportunities in the activities of citizens' assemblies.

In order to improve the legal, spiritual, moral, and physiological knowledge of parents living in mahallas related to the upbringing of the younger generation, the activities of "Parents' Universities" have been established at about 9,100 citizens' gatherings. Annually in the republic, these public structures hold more than 100 thousand events. Social partnership relations of citizens' assemblies with non-governmental non-commercial organizations, bodies of state power and administration are also developing. In particular, within the framework of measures to strengthen the "Family - Mahalla - Educational Institution" cooperation mechanism, more than 58 thousand events were organized annually in mahallas.

- In order to develop children's sports in mahallas, competitions such as "The Future of Football," "The Champions of Our Mahalla," "My Father, Mother, and I - a Family of Athletes," "We are Intelligent Families," held annually with the support of partner organizations, are of great importance. This is evidenced by the fact that about 1 million 260 thousand children and adolescents took part in the recently held republican tournament "Future of Our Football." An important factor in this is the measures taken by the Republican Charitable Public Fund "Mahalla" and its territorial subdivisions to build children's playgrounds in mahallas and further develop their activities. For example, in recent years, 1618 playgrounds have been renovated at the expense of the Republican Charitable Public Fund "Mahalla," and 701 have been built and put into operation based on standard designs.

- The work on social support and ensuring employment of vulnerable segments of the population is also noteworthy. Over the past 5 years alone, material assistance has been provided to more than 16 thousand families at the expense of the Republican Charitable Public Fund "Mahalla," clothing has been provided to about 27 thousand citizens, assistance has been provided to over 2,300 families in the repair of housing, and assistance has been provided to about 600 students with disabilities and those who have lost their breadwinner in paying for tuition.

- Within the framework of state programs, at the expense of the Republican Mahalla Charitable Public Fund, 520 war and labor veterans were provided with televisions, about 6,000 elderly people received clothing, and about 1,200 lonely elderly people received material assistance for the repair of their homes.

- The issue of ensuring employment of the population is also under constant attention. In order to support family entrepreneurship and handicrafts, the territorial subdivisions of the Republican Charitable Public Fund "Mahalla" and citizens' assemblies assisted in the creation of more than 302 thousand new jobs in the regions and the creation of more than 41 thousand business entities in the first half of this year. In this regard, a significant contribution is made by the consultation centers opened in 7,102 citizens' gatherings to promote the development of entrepreneurial activity - family entrepreneurship and handicrafts. Thanks to the efforts of mahalla activists, the spiritual atmosphere in more than 2 million families was studied in one year, and various conflicts were resolved in about 64 thousand families.

- Priority tasks for the future:

- further strengthening the spirituality of the population in mahallas;
- consistent continuation of work on social protection of the population;
- strengthening interaction with relevant state and public organizations;
- further intensification of the activities of public commissions in citizens' assemblies .

About 9 thousand self-governing bodies operating in the country carry out a wide range of activities:

- source of people's power;
- participation of citizens in public administration;
- public control;
- preservation and transmission to future generations of such national values as peace, tolerance, kindness, council, hashar, mutual assistance, generosity, and solidarity;
- strengthening the spiritual atmosphere in families;
- support for the social activity of women, protection of their rights;

- application of reconciliation procedures;
- providing assistance to low-income social strata;
- reflection of territorial historical, cultural, and geographical identity;
- ensuring the well-being and security of the mahalla;
- development of small business and family entrepreneurship.

In recent years, large-scale systemic work has been carried out to transform the mahalla institution, which is considered the most important and basic link of our society, into a true helper of the people, to create a legal framework, a management system, and institutional foundations for local self-government.

Scientific approaches aimed at determining the effective criteria of the model of local self-government, corresponding to the historical development, socio-cultural characteristics of our country, are being developed. In particular, more than 40 legislative acts related to the sphere were adopted, and more than 50 regulatory legal acts were improved. At the direct initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the country's "Obod Ko'cha," "Obod Xonadon," "Obod Mahalla," and "Yashil Makon" programs have been popularized. The Ministry for Mahalla and Family Support has been established as the authorized body of state administration for the development and implementation of a unified state policy in the field of supporting families, women, and the elderly, protecting their rights and legitimate interests, and establishing cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies .

The "Mahalla and Family" Research Institute has been established to provide scientific, methodological, and practical support for the mahalla and family support system and to conduct fundamental and innovative research in this area .

Taking into account the role of the mahalla institution in the socio-spiritual life of our society, in order to support workers in the field, March 22 was declared the Day of Mahalla System Workers.

In order to strengthen the role and significance of citizens' self-government bodies, ensure the stability of the spiritual environment on the ground, and strengthen interethnic friendship and harmony, the "Mahalla Iftikhori" badge was established.

Decree No. UP-6181 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On Approving the Concept for the Development of Civil Society for 2021-2025," adopted on March 4, 2021, played an important role in the formation of a new social, just society. Work on ensuring human rights and interests, establishing democratic principles, and increasing the social activity and legal awareness of the population has developed in society. The role of civil society institutions, including public organizations and non-governmental non-profit organizations, in the social life of society has increased. "Mahalla Center" complexes have been organized in the district and city centers, and mahalla offices have been built and reconstructed. The "growth points" of mahallas (directions of specialization) were identified, and economic growth was ensured through the implementation of "driver" projects. A system of "mahallabay" work has been introduced, providing for such priority areas as improving the entrepreneurial, investment, and competitive environment on the ground.

In order to further improve the mechanisms for ensuring employment of the population and bring the mahalla-based work system to a new level, starting from January 1, 2022, the activities of assistants to khokims of districts (cities) have been organized in mahallas. In order to implement such tasks as supporting and developing entrepreneurship in the regions together with local khokimiyats, the activities of the Agency for Mahallabay Work and

Entrepreneurship Development under the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction have been organized.

A number of important principles and programs for the spectral development of the industry are being implemented:

- the principle "mahalla - sector - People's Reception Office - mahalla";
- the principle "chairman of the mahalla - chief reformer";
- "mahallabay," "xonadonbay" work system;
- Targeted assistance system for families in need of social protection, women, and youth included in the "Iron Notebook," "Women's Notebook," and "Youth Notebook";
- a program to assist socially vulnerable segments of the population living in difficult life circumstances at the expense of the State Targeted Fund for Supporting Women and the Family;
- preservation of family values, prevention of family conflicts and divorces;
- centers for preparing young people for family life;
- National project "Yashil Makon" and others.

A new system of targeted support and social protection for women has been introduced. In particular, through the "mahallabay" system, visits were made to the homes and the problems of women were studied. More than 1 trillion 114.6 billion soums were spent almost annually to finance measures to support women included in the "Women's Notebook."

All systemic reforms serve as an important factor in the implementation of the following tasks:

1. An effective ecosystem of self-governing bodies with legal independence in solving pressing issues of local importance, based on the implementation of constitutional norms on the principle of local self-government, will be created in Uzbekistan.
2. The decentralization of power allows for the implementation of real reforms and increases the role of the population.
3. Local self-government bodies will have the opportunity to resolve various issues of local importance based on the principle of subsidiarity.
4. Increasing the role and participation of the population in making managerial decisions and political activity in solving important problems of public life.
5. Within the framework of the implementation of strategic functions between local self-government and state authorities, an effective scheme of interaction between state and local executive authorities is formed, and public control over the activities of local self-government bodies is carried out .

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